

COMPARISON BETWEEN AG AND GM AND LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The release of the massive groundbreaking paper “Simplified Rolling Calculations: Part 3 The Coupling of Degrees of Freedoms” which proved that essentially all the papers and books that deal with the marine governing (navigation) equations are fatally wrong. After the publishing of the paper, numerous reactions dealing with the coupling and relationship between the AG to GM started to stream. Clearly appearance of this tectonic size change which again proved the almost all research works done in marine engineering are basically violate either Newton’s laws and/or Thermodynamics’s law created such a reaction. The AG is the distance between the pivot point to the mass centroid while the GM is the distance between an imaginary, practically almost meaningless, point and mass centroid.

The GM dimension/parameter was used for about 300 years which has hampered the progress and the use of the GM exceeded its usefulness by far. Additionally, the comparison of the righting arm of the establishment’s theory with the righting arm on physics based model is discussed. These two issues were not addressed in the breakthrough paper, thus this paper was written. While this paper is not in the same league as the said paper, yet it still provides significant information. In the first part, a discussion on the relationship of GM and AG for three geometries is presented. Additionally, in the later part, the recent papers dealing with GM are discussed. Please note that the typical responds of the leading establishment’s the supper great scientists such as O. Faltinsen, T. Fossen, C. Judge, Christopher Kent, Frederick Stern, and etc or even same level or better such his excellence scientist as the supreme Dr. Yamaka (escaped from Borat Culture adventure), in the approach “if we don’t see it, it does not exist”. See the call of Disputation at the end of the paper.

It was shown that the GM functionality does not behave in the same way as the AG . These two quantities have different dependencies and functionalities. Review of typical fatal errors in the literature is offered. In the rsymmetry (horizontal movement of the pivot point), is another area that affects the GM and the AG is discussed. The GM is independent of the input angle θ for unrsymmetrical bodies (left of right) according the establishment’s logic while in physics based model AG depends on the input angle. The change in the vertical direction of the pivot point is linear while for angle in the angle out can lead to instability. While in the establishment’s theory the GM is essentially the fixed. The spread of the information will be inexorable. Indeed, the information as the most read papers on RG thus already appears now to be inevitable to stop the establishment’s nonsense.

NOMENCLATURE

Points of Interest

A, A', A'' Pivot point at the liquid level

b Width of the body

\bar{b} The ratio of b_1/b_2

B Buoyancy centroid

G Mass centroid

K Keel

M Metacenter none existent and imaginary point

\emptyset Point on vertical after input angle

Z A point on GM perpendicular to B

Λ A point on the liquid line crossing the counter left side

χ A point on the liquid line crossing the counter rightsize

Variables

a trapezoid dimension Coefficient

b trapezoid dimension Coefficient

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c trapezoid dimension Coefficient
 D Total Ship (body) height
 \mathcal{D} New distance \mathcal{B}'
 d Ship draft
 g Gravity constant
 I Moment of inertia either body or liquid
 \mathcal{L} Lagrangian
 L Angular momentum
 m Mass
 s Ship Length
 t Time
 \mathcal{T} Kinetic energy
 \mathcal{U} Potential energy
 w Ship weight
 \mathfrak{X} Horizontal distance to the original pivot point
 x Distance in straight (movement) direction
 y Distance perpendicular to x

Greek Letters

α Absolute value of difference angle right to left
 β Triangle letter as α sometimes
 ω Angular velocity
 ϕ Angle based on pivot at \mathbf{G} (commonly undefined)
 ρ Density
 θ Input Angle
 ξ The angle $\angle AKA'$

Subscripts

0 Old location
 1 Triangle 1
 2 Triangle 2
 add, a Added mass/force
 b Floating body (ship)
 ℓ left
 r right
 xx Around the x coordinate

Key Words

Ship Rolling, Added Mass matrix, \mathbf{GM} , \mathbf{AG} , Parametric Rolling, Pivot Points

1 Introduction

Bouguer invented the metacenter (a primitive concept/mechanism) to evaluate the stability of the ship (Bouguer 1746). Since then, this invention of the metacenter has not only been dominated but exclusive way to measure stability in the marine engineering field until this author developed the angle in and angle out principal. The metacenter, an imaginary, non precise and only sometime indirectly related to the stability, is entrenched deeply in the field. It seems that even today the metacenter concept is heavily used but in an erroneous way which is one of the core topic of this article. In fact, even after

this author demonstrated conclusively that \mathbf{GM} is not directly related to the righting arm (the force less the righting arm for the ship) (Bar-Meir 2023g) it still heavily used by many in the industry. A review on some recent papers is provided below to demonstrate this point. Furthermore, it seems that there are “researchers/scientists” who believe that the pivot point is at the metacenter (this information never reach them, they just live under a rock). This kind of papers suggests that these authors should be shamed to the largest possible degree to prevent this nonsense to continue.

The major breakthroughs that occurred recently in marine engineering are: 1) locations of the pivot points and their movements in addition to that the change of the added mass verses the erroneous added mass matrix. The added mass matrix, another erroneous and conclusive used concept has dominated the marine engineering. The added mass matrix is based on the erroneous impression that velocity components are independent while simply state velocity is based its components. Thus, using the velocity components in calculation of the forces violates of Newton’s laws and therefore the second laws thermodynamics (Bar-Meir 2024c). The pivot points control the floating body moment of inertia and the added moment of inertia. The change of body moment of inertia and the added mass is the correct physics alternative view of the body dynamics. In addition, the fatal errors of the added matrix must be eliminated (Bar-Meir 2024c).

Some esoteric research works are presented for the understanding of some of the effects of the \mathbf{GM} . A floating body with uniform density has typically buoyancy centroid blow the mass centroid. Actual floating body like ship has the mass centroid some what lower as some of the heavy items (engine for example) stationed lower. Or the arrangement can be the opposite. In the extreme case, \mathbf{G} can be lower or higher than \mathbf{B} . In some of these cases, \mathbf{GM} might be negative (in extreme cases) and yet the ship stay stable. One would expect that, most of the time, the positive \mathbf{GM} means that the ship or the floating body is somewhat stable at least in a calm liquid. Watanabe (1934) studied the negative \mathbf{GM} (this twilight dome scenario) and its effects on the governing equation. Watanabe concluded that the ship can be somewhat stable even with negative \mathbf{GM} . In other words, in a traditional perception, conceptually a negative \mathbf{GM} should make the governing equation totally unstable is not correct. Additionally to the forgoing, Watanabe assumed that the pivot point is at metacenter but in the real complicated at the point \mathbf{A} . This error in Watanabe logic since in reality the ship is not rotating around this point. While the math/physics of the paper seems to be resalable yet without the full understanding the words, it is impossible to be conclusive and remark on this paper in a definitive way. Nevertheless, the standard approach basically assumes that the negative \mathbf{GM} means that the body is unstable and yet this perception might not be correct. While “feature” of the establishment’s method has no clear limit (as it

was discussed above) while the angle in angle out method has a clear cut boarder. Thus in this department, the angle in and angle out concept (precursor to the pivot point concept) point is a way superior.

FIGURE 1. A schematic to explain the rolling for negative GM after Watanabe (1928).

In their master thesis (at that the time a couple of people were joining in writing the master thesis.) Clarke and Noble (1923) studied the roll effects on the gun shot. What interesting, at least for this author, is the usage the mass centroid as a pivot point vs the metacenter that everyone was using at time. As this thesis was written in 1923 (maybe 1922) this usage is unique was seem to be the first (previously this author found only works with pivot point with mass centroid in 195x). Perhaps, one examiner (maybe adviser) was from MIT (Allyne L. Merrill 1863 – February 26, 1941 and that is the reason to the added new twists.

An extract taken from (Kato 1936) shows that the confusion of results from the change of moment of inertia but physical poor understanding of what is really going on.

Quotations

It was found from the experimental results that the apparent moment of inertia increases with the amplitude even though the period of roll decreases, and that i:o theoretical formulae neglecting its variation give a correct value of period for any specified amplitude, particularly for ships fitted with deep bilge keels.

Reference: Kato 1936

While the topic AG vs GM was addressed in (Bar-Meir 2024b) but the question of the functionality was not discussed. Even the indirectly observed but recognized vertical movements of the pivot pointed by Kato which were not investigated. Is the functionality change the constant and the slop (assuming it is linear) or are the relationships different? Is the establishment's approach, especially when the moment of inertia is variable, is

applicable or reasonable and the wrong righting arm just need a small modification? Another issue with the variable GM due to the waves which changing the value of GM in pitching (changing the list) was investigated by Watanabe (1934). Watanabe concluded that GM can be obtain a negative value when he was hampered by the lack of understanding of the real governing equation. Since the GM is not actually and directly affecting the righting arm, there are mistakes in the logic and the governing equations.

FIGURE 2. A schematic to explain the rolling for negative GM after Watanabe (1934).

The variation of the GM with the appearance or the presence of the wave was concerned by many researchers. Fincham (1851) discuss the stability of the triangle cross section floating with a GM fixed in time. Karata (2024) continue in the belief that added mass coefficients are constant i.e. violations of Newton law and wrong pivot points among the standard errors. How in the world one expect to get realistic results when using the wrong governing equations with the wrong assumptions. Especially when the whole department in Gdańsk, Poland was informed and shown that the establishment model/method simply violates basics physics laws.

2 GM Calculations

In this section, comparison between three different geometries of the establishment's method instead of the real physical approach. In this comparison the topic such as rsymmetry (rotation symmetry) are shown and advocate to use the new technology. This comparison is based on basic and simple principles. While the negative GM discussion is mostly for non uniform density the following discussion is for uniform density.

2.1 Rectangle Shape

Rectangular shape is rsymmetrical (rotational symmetry) shape (Bar-Meir 2024b) and hence this shape seems at first glance the best geometry in which better matching can be found. The common GM is calculated by the equation as (Bar-Meir 2022b, any

Fig. 11.

FIGURE 3. A schematic to explain the rolling for negative \mathbf{GM} after Watanabe (1934). Notice that Watanabe instinctively draw the pivot point in the right location (moving horizontal). Yet he did not understand his discovery and its significant.

version of the book since 2020)

$$\mathbf{GM} = \frac{I_{xx}}{V_0} - \mathbf{GB} \quad (1)$$

where I_{xx} is moment of inertia at the water level with a pivot at center of the water line and V_0 is the submerged volume. Looking at the definition/equation, one should wonder why the establishment did not realized or got the hint that the pivot point is at the point \mathbf{A} (since moment inertia already at the liquid level). Equation (1) can be also written for a solid body with a constant density as

$$\mathbf{GM} = \frac{\rho_\ell I_{xx}}{\rho_s V_{body}} - \mathbf{GB} \quad (2)$$

For the rectangular/square shape (Bar-Meir 2022b, section 10.2)

$$\frac{\mathbf{GM}}{D} = \frac{1}{12} \left(\frac{b}{D} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\rho_\ell}{\rho_s} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\rho_s}{\rho_\ell} \right) \quad (3)$$

It can be noticed as the ratio of $\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_\ell}$ is not simply a linear function but a complex and in one range increase the size of \mathbf{GM} as it was shown in (Bar-Meir 2022b).

However the \mathbf{AG} can be expressed in dimensionless form as $\mathbf{AG}/D = (1 - \rho_s/\rho_\ell)/2$ is linearly depends on the density ratio. This part is related to the righting arm and prediction is different for the erroneous establishment model verses the physics based model. A summary of the analysis is the establishment and the physics based model produces different results and ten-

dency.

2.2 Unsymmetrical and Symmetrical Triangle Cross Section

There are two cases of the symmetrical triangle one) is the narrow side down and two) the narrow side is up. Even without the mathematics, one can be observed that the case triangle narrow pointing down as shown in fig. 4 the \mathbf{GB} distance is larger for narrow side up. This case deals with unsymmetrical (and symmetrical) triangle shown in fig. 4 where points of interest are located $B = 2d/3$ and $G = 2d/3$. The relationship between d

FIGURE 4. A schematic to explain the distance of \mathbf{GB} and the calculation of \mathbf{GM} for triangle. Note the locations of points of interest are precisely measured.

and D is obtained from Archimedes's equation. The width as a function of the height is $b(d) = d \tan \beta$. Knowing that depth, s does not play a role which leads to

$$\rho_s \frac{D^2 \tan \beta}{2} = \rho_\ell \frac{d^2 \tan \beta}{2} \quad (4)$$

or in a simplified form as

$$d = D \sqrt{\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_\ell}} \quad (5)$$

This relationship is similar to the rectangular relationship but weaker.

The moment of inertia at the liquid level assuming that the pivot point is the center line (establishment model's error)

of the body and thus

$$I_{xx} = \frac{b^3 s}{12} \quad (6)$$

where s is the depth dimension of the prism (into the page). The volume of the submerged volume is $V_0 = d^2 \tan \beta s/2$. The distance, \mathbf{GB} can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{GB} = \frac{2}{3}(D-d) = \frac{2D}{3} \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_\ell}}\right) \quad (7)$$

In this case the \mathbf{GM} is

$$\mathbf{GM} = \frac{\overbrace{\frac{I_{xx}}{d^2 \tan \beta}}^{\frac{12}{d^2 \tan \beta}} - \frac{2D}{3} \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_\ell}}\right)}{\underbrace{2}_{V_0}} \quad (8)$$

or in a simplified form as

$$\frac{\mathbf{GM}}{D} = \left(\frac{(\tan^2 \beta)}{6} + \frac{2}{3} \right) \sqrt{\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_\ell}} - \frac{2}{3} \quad (9)$$

The point where $\mathbf{GM} = 0$ is at

$$\sqrt{\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_\ell}} = \frac{4}{((\tan^2 \beta) + 4)} \quad (10)$$

As it was shown else where (Watanabe), this point does not mean that this point where the body become unstable.

It is interesting that in this unrealistic analysis (this analysis is correct only if \mathbf{GM} influence realistic but unfortunately it is not.) relationship or association to the righting arm is linear while in reality the relationship is non-continuous complicated function. These dissimilar functions cannot be confused as similar as the establishment's scientists claim.

2.3 Circular Cross Section

The circular shape is the only relatively simple geometry that provides identical answers from both establishment's method and the physics based model. The explanation for this strange identical answers is because another argument (it must be zero for uniform density). The calculations for the \mathbf{GM} are essen-

tially going over the steps in the regular procedure outline in (Bar-Meir 2022b) or (Bar-Meir 2022a). The relationship of a cylinder lays flat on the liquid with a depth s into page and radius r . While the answer could be obtained just by knowing that \mathbf{GM} should be zero (for constant density) and for symmetry reason for angle in angle out. However, this material is a draft for the stability book and hence these derivations are shown. The liquid level is assumed to be below the cylinder centroid (as shown the fig. 5). Calculating the \mathbf{GM} for this orientation and geometry, first noticing that the cross section of solid at the liquid level has a rectangular shape (little imagination). The volume of cylinder is $V_o = \pi r^2 s$ and the moment of inertia is $I = sb^3/12$. Where s is the depth (length) of the cylinder, $b = 2\sqrt{2rd-d^2}$, and β is shown in fig. 5. Repeating the steps described before to get \mathbf{GM} .

FIGURE 5. A schematic to explain the dimension of cylinder/circle

The d is the submerged depth, $D = 2r$ and the calculations are done for the lower half $0 \geq d \geq r$. The angle is

$$\beta = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{r-d}{r} \right) \quad (11)$$

The ratio of area of sector (for 2β) is

$$\frac{A_s}{A_o} = \frac{\int \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{r-d}{r} \right)}{\int \pi} \quad (12)$$

where A_s is the sector area and A_o is the whole circle area. The area of the sector is

$$A_s = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{r-d}{r} \right) r^2 \quad (13)$$

Examining the fig. 5 shows that the segment area is

$$A_{segment} = A_s - A_{\Delta} = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{r-d}{r} \right) r^2 - \frac{\lambda (r-d) \sqrt{2dr-d^2}}{\lambda} \quad (14)$$

Applying the requirement that the wight of the floating body is the same as the displaced (Archimedes).

$$V_0 \rho_{\ell} = V_{body} \rho_s \longrightarrow A_{segment} \rho_{\ell} = A_o \rho_s \quad (15)$$

Resulting in

$$\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_{\ell}} \pi = \cos^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{d}{r} \right) - \left(1 - \frac{d}{r} \right) \sqrt{2 \frac{d}{r} - \left(\frac{d}{r} \right)^2} \quad (16)$$

FIGURE 6. Various parts of circle as a function of the density ratio.

3 Review of Erroneous Usage of GM Past and Current

This discussion starts with a thesis that was recently published as writing this paper while others publications (that will be discussed) gained or already have long tenured. Thus, it is important to expose these fallacious ideas. Zhou (2024) study the bending (forces and torques acting of ship and the ship re-

sponses to those forces) using Timoshenko’s beam theory as the effect of the wave or the hydraulic forces. While the application of Timoshenko’s theory of ship is questionable, the main issue is the governing equations. As usual, the cascading backward leads to the underline effects which are the pivot points and the righting arms. It is more than strange that the authors simply ignored the material published showing the torque is a function of the pivot point. Even logically, the torque is a function of the force and distance to the pivot point and thus the pivot points is very important. For example in equation (2.1 and 2.4) the author decided that the added masses coefficients are constant without any logic even though it was shown to be erroneous. In the text below equation (2.1), the author alleged that the reaction is time-harmonic is true only for perfect rsymmetrical body. Even then, the stiffness matrix requires that pivot point should be accounted for. Notice that a remark on effect on the added mass on the structure should be included at least in theory but this topic is avoided as it was not fully analyzed by this author. The section “Linear Radiation Problem” simply ignore the (Bar-Meir 2024c) and thus it simply rubbish.

Moreira et al (2007) studied the tanker Esso Osaka and described how to “control” the tanker. As usual, these authors chose the mass centroid as the origin and this work includes the standard errors of pivot points at the mass centroid (fundamental error). Additionally, these authors use their **lack** of basics of fluid mechanics knowledge and it is exposed when even a simple operation like dimensional analysis was not performed properly (see equation 1 for example, reducing to a primitive idea). The authors assumed also that added mass matrix is applicable (wrong) and the mass coefficients are constant (see table 4 in the paper). Additionally to these errors, the authors reduced the 6 DOF to to 4 DOFs without any real logical (better to state erroneous logic). In fact, the “logic” is from kinematic point of view and not physical as the authors were concerned with 2-D direction movement. The logic of the rudder and the time scale seems unreasonable but here it will not discussed since these topics are not really clear. Yet, all the equations such as (45) and related are basically erroneous.

Russo et al (2024) studied the floating breakwaters because they believe the importance of this devices. The importance of this study is left out but the way the governing equations and the assumptions are set up is the focus. The cross section shape is part of circle and triangle attached on the top (see figure 1a in the paper). This configuration has issue on the point of unrsymmetrical and it is not continuous as it as demonstrated in (Bar-Meir 2024b). The real analysis shows that righting arm is a very complicated function of the geometry and defiantly not depend on **GM**. In their paper, equation (1) claims that $GM_T = KB + BM_T - KG$. What the metacenter has to do with the stability of device? The pivot point is not at the meta-center and the righting arm is not direct function of **GM**. The authors calculated the moment of inertia without even know-

ing what are the pivot points (is that new physics? What nice it would be if the moment of inertia can be calculated regardless to pivot point! See table 2 in the paper.). According the authors (citing Faltinsen a guy known as the responsible person to produce so many erroneous ideas in marine engineering) the device is a simple pendulum. Seeing so many errors in the paper, one cannot stop and wonder if these authors should take a class in basic of physics before tackling bigger problems or simply read the literature review. For instance, equation (4) in that paper describing the decay coefficients if indeed it come out clean from the right governing equation. However these “decay coefficients” should include the change of the added mass and the change of pivot points which they did not include. Without these effects included, it is like measuring the height of the child by measuring the child liver activity.

Additionally, the authors claimed that the frequency in rolling is (citing (Russo, Contestabile, Vicinanza, and Lugni 2024))

$$\omega_{roll} = \sqrt{\frac{\rho g V_0 \mathbf{GM}}{I_{roll} + A_{roll}}} \quad (17)$$

This equation was debunked so many times in the past that is strange that anyone is still used it. The obvious question how these moment of inertia are calculated without claiming or knowing the correct pivot point. The same can be said for the added mass because the value is also depends on the pivot point (for the rolling). The same can be said on the pitch while yaw is more complicated. Hence, equation (4) is totally wrong as there several other mistakes. What follow is a simple gibberish mass that now can explained. Check figure (5) which not related to what is shown in figure.

One group or university that like to double down on stupidity is Gdańsk where Krata et al (Krata, Gil, Hinz, and Koziol 2024) produced another paper that can only exist in the fairy tale realm. For example, consider the statement

Quotations

Despite the contemporary 6DOF models can be used to predict ship motions in irregular waves ... from the abstract of the paper!

Reference: Krata et al 2024

Now, it is well established that the establishments’ governing equations for the six degree of freedom are simply violate Newtons and second law thermodynamics (Bar-Meir 2023a; Bar-Meir 2023c; Bar-Meir 2023e) for several reasons. First, the pivot points are in the wrong locations and hence contravene the second of thermodynamics, second, the added mass matrix transgress the kinematic and Newtons laws and by extension the second law thermodynamics. The added mass matrix is

based on the velocity components are independent of the total velocity. The authors are citing numerous works known to be erroneous these citations does not make the authors claims any valid. Are these researchers expecting that combining multiply errors works somehow in way to remedy fatal errors if they are taken collectively. While the authors admitted (private communication) that they not understand the added mass matrix, using the added mass matrix does not added quality to their work, the added mass matrix is simply wrong.

Greco et al (2015) “studied” the sway–yaw interaction while claiming that the interaction is the effect on parametric rolling. According some of the definitions, the parametric rolling refers to or caused by the appearance of wave(s) that effecting ship. It is not surprising that one of the authors, Faltinsen, who in large part single handily responsible to introduce the second most significant error (rotational potentials) to produce this paper. While the authors are confused and believe that mostly the roll–yaw (see definitions of ship motions in (Bar-Meir 2022a)) are responsible for the phenomenon.

Quotations

PR is recognized to be induced by changes in the transverse metacentric height (GM) and so in the restoring properties of the vessel caused by the interaction with incident waves and by sufficiently large heave and pitch motions.

Reference: Greco et al 2015

However, the parametric rolling (what these authors call PR) is not caused by the change in GM (but the effective or active density). This instability can be explained by simply looking at the angle in angle out analysis and checking when the ship is stepping out the stability dome (see (Bar-Meir 2022a; Bar-Meir 2021)). Moreover, the parametric rolling is not directly related to the incident wave angle as claimed by these authors (not surprising this claim can be shown to be totally false under some conditions). In another meaningless quote the authors claim that

Quotations

... and period, that tend to be aligned to the vessel longitudinal axis and are associated with a natural roll frequency-to-incident wave frequency ratio $\omega_{4n}/\omega = 0.5, 1, 2$ and so on.

Reference: Faltinsen 2015 and 198x...

The natural frequency does not depend on the GM but on AG and it is not a simple function. It was shown that the possible frequency is not linearly connected to the next frequency in the series (because the frequency depends on the angle). Furthermore, the natural frequency also changes due to the change in AG and not GM which occurs due to the wave. The establishment’s model predicts that parametric rolling occurs because the wave while the physics based model points to to exiting from

the stability model. As a proof to this idea, the frequency is not linear function and thus the establishment model is wrong. Additionally, the authors discussed the combination of sway-roll-yaw which the two DOFs roll and yaw affecting the sway but the sway not affecting the other two. The idea that these DOFs are connection is based on the added mass matrix which is erroneous (Bar-Meir 2024c).

Phuong et al (2024) studied the roll motion of the ship Bettica believing that the establishment erroneous equations describing the roll and the roll decay correctly. Beside the idea that the added mass is fix, the author belief that the real dimensional analysis is not really required to build a proper scale model. As common, the definition of the roll angle is missing but it seems to be around the mass centroid (note there is no really a precise definition in the paper. Who let this low quality paper and ref (20) of that paper be published?). The righting moment is guessed (Phuong did not state it) or assumed at the wrong pivot point (maybe the mass centroid? Which is wrong!). In any case, the analysis is living in fantasy realm and has nothing with reality of the ship movement.

Yu et al (2024) studied the ship maneuverability with a dual full rotary propulsion. This paper is example how the marine alchemy is at work. While is clear that the authors put a lot of efforts in this fantastic work from the fairy tale realm, one should wonder why not use science in this area. The authors use four degree of freedoms, and the MMG concept which is known to be wrong. What happened to the two other degree of freedoms that were not used (did these two degree of freedom effects disappeared? Why?). For start, the concept of four degree of freedoms is based on the added mass matrix which violates the Newton's law and by extension the second law of thermodynamics (Bar-Meir 2024c). As side point, the authors alleged that pivot point is at the mass centroid but this claim violates the second law of thermodynamics. The authors somehow believe that GM or the change of the GM are responsible for parametric rolling $\Delta GM/GM$ is large and used this belief to obtain experimental values without conducting a proper dimensional analysis. This non physical explanation has several logic problems. According to the authors the equation is dimensional while the left hand side is a non dimensional (at least according to their statements). Beside this claim, the GM does not affect the stability directly (Bar-Meir 2023g). The fact that their work shows that experimental results does not follow their model ("load cases except LC3 and LC5 failed") is a strong indication that their work is simply nonsense. There are several other mistakes in this work such as constant added mass, usage of added mass matrix etc.

Taylan studied (2020) the GM under the assumption that the rotation is at the metacenter. Since this paper at the time when the scientific revolution started, this nonsense idea can be forgiven. Taylan, Kanifolskyi et al (2016), Dunworth (2013), and Karolius et al (2018) all which did not asked the most funda-

mental question where is the pivot point. While the GM value and/or dimension is insignificant point and yet it attracts considerable attention. For example in Taylan (2020) equation (3) the angle is forced to be related to the metacenter while in other papers by the same author show that the authors believe that pivot point is at mass centroid. This confusion is typical for people in marine engineering who really lake of basics of physics knowledge. See for example,

Figure 2. Inclined ship by test weights.

FIGURE 7. A schematic to explain the inclination for block locations and assuming pivot point at metacenter.

Düz (2020) studied the sensitivity and the parametric rolling which he referred to as a non linear effect (which he does not understand as it is coupling effect). Every once in a while small amount of knowledge is piercing the establishment's cloak of idiocy and provides interesting point. Of course many times this discovery is done unintentionally (as not aware what was discovered) as seems in this case. The added mass matrix idea dictates that all the 6 degree of freedoms must be activated every time any degree of freedom flares. In in this case with realizing, the author stated that

Quotations

Parametric roll resonance typically occurs in head or following sea conditions (or very close to head or following). Normally in pure head or following long-crested seas, a transversely symmetric ship will experience pitch, heave and surge motion, but no transverse roll moment. However, if the ship experiences certain wave encounter frequencies, a rolling motion can occur.

Reference: Düz 2020

The idea that a wave creates only selective movements such as pitch(rotation), heave (up and down), and surge (foreword and backward) is contradict the added mass matrix logic which believe that all the degree of motions must be activated once one is activated (Bar-Meir 2024c). Clearly Düz did not consider this idea but sheer fact that he and others actually observed it demonstrate that idea of added mass matrix instinctively was

know to be false by many. The rest of the paper full of typical mistakes which include but not limited to fixed added mass (not withstanding the previous remark showing conflict with fixed added mass, how the author did not see that and miss this important issue).

Mai et al (2022) studied the roll utilizing the full 6 degree of freedoms and the authors believed that small GM and high speed determine or dominate the rolling mechanism. As a first remark on this work is at the coordinate system used. The authors assumed that the pivot points are at the mass centroid which of course is wrong (not to mentioned the wrong locations as not all of them in the same locations.). These errors continue to bleed into other areas and it culminates in the governing equation (2) used by the authors. While the authors insinuation that GM was calculate either because the paper was in the fairy tale realm or because they did not find what to calculate, it does not seem to the case. Mai et al paper is based on a large extend on the paper of (2022) (very little originality) which contains the same mistakes. Side remark, who are the reviewers of this paper? Did these reviewers check for plagiarizing? These authors believe that somehow without the physics just crunching the numbers provides the answers utilizing the erroneous equations. Really?

Woo et al (2021) advocating the usage of the software to control the ship stability using specific package. Unfortunately the software is based on the erroneous concepts and ideas.

Quotations

For the safe navigation of ships, maintaining sufficient stability according to International Maritime Organization (IMO) stability regulations is essential.

Reference: Woo 2021

Beside the spelling mistake (maybe new word?) in the quotation, one must puzzle about reliance the IMO organization standard in regards to the ship stability. The fact that the main purpose/concept is based on the GM is strong indication that this organization/committee is based on individuals who really do not understand the subject matter. For example, one of the point in the paper is based on (2019) which based of the “measured” GM on ship frequencies only if this functionality was truly available. How exactly one measures the GM (is must be measuring frequency and equation for GM is wrong.).

This paper cited the paper (Unit 2006) related to “IMO intact stability parameters of 336 loading conditions of 19 model ships.” This fact that so many criteria are used to check for stability is strong indication that they do not know what they are doing. In all these cases, the first question is where the pivot point so that the useless and not reflective GZ should not not enters the calculations (GZ should not be used).

Deleanu et al (2020) attempted to study the idea of the change velocity of the ship during heave so that the change in

GM somehow prevent the parametric rolling (basically the effect of surge on heave). It asses the idea without proper description of the situation and when what should change during the process. At this stage, the examination was focused on the equations and less on the concept because this idea is moot. However, the equations written in the paper are erroneous. In this case (and maybe others), the authors believe the Maclaurin series to represent the wave(s) without any argument (why?). Where these authors consider or even aware that the section of Maclaurin series vs Fourier series creates different solutions (why not carry a literature review). This point not a criticism on the section but on the fact that no explanation is provided or argued. The governing equation full of errors such as constant added mass and several others that means that calculations are in the fairy tale realm.

Giallanza et al (2020) provided a case study of a large yacht stability with the same typical errors such the pivot point at the mass centroid. For example consider the statement

Quotations

It is known how the metacentric method can be applied to small angles and therefore hypothesize that the projection on the XY transversal plane of the trajectory of the center of buoyancy center B is an arc of a circle, with center of the arc in the transverse metacenter M.

Reference: Giallanza et al 2020

According to the authors someone knows how metacenter method can be applied. Except that this idea is simply wrong. See for example figure (3) for the pivot point. What is amazing the fact that the drawing shows miraculously that the displacement did not change which is not possible. Notice the inconsistency where in figure 4, on the left the pivot point is at point A in the same figure on the right of the pivot point is at the metacenter.

Takeda et al (2023) studied the parametric rolling. According these authors and their sources, the mechanism is based on the location (that is not really physical but locations on the cycle roll when and where the (in)stability occurs). The reason that they cannot explain their idea in physical terms is because they still using living with the metacenter as a pivot point. Furthermore, they do not attempt to look at the problem from the physical point of view. But as a small progress the authors recommend to ignore the natural roll periods based on the 2008 IS Code as it is a pure nonsense. In other words, periods is based on the square root of GM which is not physical (Bar-Meir 2024b; Bar-Meir 2023g). In the governing equation (5) the authors claimed that the damping is in the third order of the angular velocity without provide the logical physics based explanation for it. Of course it does not matter as the main terms that involve with the added mass change do not appear in the equation at all.

Maruyama et al (2022) studied the parametric rolling when they alleged that the heave (what they called the wave or due to the wave) causing the change in GM . According this ideology they can use mathematical tools like non-Gaussian process and combine change in the GM with other mathematical tools. Without going through the mathematics it can be argue that “measurements” of the change GM are wrong because they were using the wrong governing equations. Using sophisticate tool does not solve problem if the governing equations are not really based on the physical principle. In another paper Maruyama et al (2024) used “enhance” experimental tool to study to maximum roll angle by “using improved swarm intelligent optimization, time series decomposition, and machine learning.” His logic is correct that with the establishment’s method it is not possible to calculations of the roll motion. The suggestion is basically do not use science but guessing game. This idea is appropriate for the case where nothing is known that even dimensional analysis cannot be employed. This idea seems to be overreach as today there is physics base model that provide the ability to analysis the situation. The author provided several statements that one wonder why the authors did done proper literature review or consider their statements

Katsumura et al (2024) suggested to used only the wave component based on the Froude–Krylov’s assumption. Of course, this assumption is not reasonable. Appropriate approach is to use the coupling equations that control the situation. In these equations the change in the added mass has to lead to the calculations of the elapsed time that ship or floating body is under or over the GM (GM is used here to be in the same terminology as the authors. Actually GM is wrong and the correct term is AG). Since the physics was not clear (really correct) to the author without doing proper dimensional analysis the authors done experimental study. Since the authors harbor deep lake of knowledge the physics they use statistical tools.

Xu et al (2024) suggested that the roll motion cannot be explained.

Quotations

Currently, ship motion status prediction is mainly categorized into two modes based on hydrodynamics and non-hydrodynamics, respectively.

Reference: Xu et al

For example, consider the statement above which the strange “non-hydrodynamics” is used and no one can explain it. It this force is electrical?

At the birth place of the terminal error of added mass matrix Kim et al (2021) still propagating this error and others. For example check the equations (3)–(8) of the paper for the full 6 Degree of freedom. With a poor man dimensional analysis the authors try to verified their erroneous research with “experi-

mental” not really related to the model. Again with typical erroneous idea rotation around the body mass centroid (violation of second law thermo) and many other mistakes such as the wrong righting arm etc who is the one that expect to get anything that live in the reality. Maruyama et al (2024), with realizing it, work to prove that work like Xu et al (2024) (is Stern, Frederick the principle of this nonsense?) is wrong because they used statistical (read experimental work) means to study the parametric rolling. Clearly if any of these “researchers” work had any validity their model will not require statistical analysis.

4 Summary

This paper is reaction to the stream of emails that the main author received from kind of questions that needed some clarifications. The clear reactions to (Bar-Meir 2024c) and earlier papers have been significant so additional information was needed. The request dealt with application or actual difference between the erroneous establishment method vs physics based model. The only geometry in which the two methods was circular shape other wise in in simple geometry like rectangular differences in functionality and ranges are very significant. A examination of some of the work with emphasis on the recent show that many researchers are living under the rock and like to hide the head in the sand like individuals such as Faltinsen, and Fossen. Also with actually solving several reasoning where offered these “researchers” to parametric rolling which indicate there is significant lake of knowledge in this area.

The Establishment

A passive aggressive letter that the leading author received from an establishment personality and it is indicative of their attitude to ward science.

“ Good evening,
I would encourage you to get your paper into a peer reviewed journal (understanding that is a long and arduous process) so you can get feedback from experts in the field and further develop your arguments. I looked through your paper and stand unconvinced of your baseline argument that off axis coupling terms are unphysical (with no real evidence). You also seem to ignore the inertial reference frame part of the formulation of those EOMs.
Journals that come to mind are the Journal of Ship Research (I am an associate editor) and Ship Technology Research but I am sure there are many others.
Best of luck with your research endeavors.
Christopher Kent

The following is a reply to Christopher Kent from DARPA

and others DARPA or from any organizations who believes in the same idea (**it does not exist, if I say that I do see it**) as a reaction to this authors papers.

Dear Dr. Chris Kent,

Thank you for your feedback. I appreciate that you at least “read” the paper. I did not solicit your response or your advice but I glad that you attempting to raise a defense (actually it is deflection but it also okay) for the establishment ideas. I do not think that you are in a position to give me advice how to publish my papers/ideas. The situation is strange to you as you have to counter the claims leveled in this article and preceding papers that your journal published papers that are violating the basics physics laws as we know it. First, this paper (Bar-Meir 2024c) is already published, and it is well read (you can see the statistics the paper was at 100% read and now it is at 99%). Thank you very much for the “generous” “possibility” to be published in your journal and references will review this article and other papers. Your suggestion make no sense, how people who are clueless like yourself can provide an advice or review on something that they do not understand? Yes, Bar-Meir questions the credibility of your references and their motives. Do you really think that a person that is criticized and shown that his work is basically is worthless will be objective or/and knowledgeable (assuming that he/she has any real knowledge on these topics.).

You stated that you do not “convinced.” It is either that you do not understand the ideas in paper or select to not to understand material (clearly you did not read the references. Your claim “You also seem to ignore the inertial reference frame part of the formulation of those EOMs.”) What is “inertial reference frame” pivot point in mass centroid? Because your strange English, it is not possible to make sense of your statement. I will guess what you actually say. First, the frame of reference is only way humans attempt to understand the physics, while reality frame of reference meaningless. The choice of the frame of reference does not change physics. Assuming that you mean that the frame of reference is attached to mass centroid which was proven to be violating the Newton and second law of thermodynamics. So why use this irrelevant frame of reference? The ship or the body does not rotate around mass centroid but in point \mathcal{A} (see the definition in reference)? Your frame of reference does not make the understanding clearer. The actual pivot point should determine the frame of reference.

Basically, these papers series demonstrate that almost all the papers publish in your journal and other journals are erroneous in my colorful language are described as trash. Thus, your statement “... unconvinced of your baseline argument that off axis coupling terms are unphysical (with no real evidence)”. It seems that you write as Biden’s talk; just mesh potato. I have no idea what you mean, and I am sure that you also do not know as well what you meant. So let me restate the fundamentals: 1) the added mass matrix is wrong and fundamentally violates the basics core physical principles. 2) the governing equations used

by various establishment individuals like you are simply wrong because the pivot point are not in the metacenter or mass centroid (inertial reference frame).

Your claim about “inertial reference frame” suggests you suffer from lake of understanding about the pivot point. This claim is a typical of people who did not study proper physics. This point is discussed extensively in the papers (Bar-Meir 2022b; Bar-Meir 2021; Bar-Meir 2024a; Bar-Meir 2023f; Bar-Meir 2023e; Bar-Meir 2023c; Bar-Meir 2023b; Bar-Meir 2023a; Bar-Meir 2023g; Bar-Meir 2024b; Bar-Meir 2024c). It is recommended that you read also the establishment story in die casting (Bar-Meir 2023d).

Just wonder why you do not continue to defend the establishment logic or models. I am willing to be in a disputation with an opposing panel of 20 experts (you can select anyone in the world) and I will be humiliated if I am wrong (I take the risk, will you?).

Prediction

It is rarely or hardly ever happened when one individual make discoveries that basically evince that the whole field (with billions of dollars invested in research grants) is totally futile. Not surprising that minions and establishment’s figures such as you (Christopher Kent from DARPA) are attacking this individual. The first author has already made a revolution in die casting where he changed the whole field upside down. The question that raised how long it will take to insert the knowledge into marine engineering. In die casting it took about 35 years where the establishment basically had major controlled the publishing avenues. Initially in the process and as results of conflict this author faced many obstacles. Later the main location of “science” (Ohio State University) seems to be melting away because the shame of the trashy research work that done by the main faculty because all was exposed.

The question how long it will take to learn (to teach) the correct governing equations (new technologies). There are those who publicly put their head in the sand such as Faltinsen, Fossen, and Carlos Guedes Soares, and Skjetne and several Korean, Japanese researchers and etc. While in die casting this stage was about 25 years, in marine engineering, a larger field such as marine engineering it is hope to be shorter. For one, the research grants in die casting are only less than 1% as compared to marine engineering which is about 5 billions dollars. Perhaps, with the billions of dollars the establishment will be able to produce erroneous research for much longer. Yet, the opposite effect the spread information speed today is much significant, thus the process might be faster.

Disputation

After the minion Mathias Mathias from Norwegian University of Science and Technology and probably his masters (it hard to believe graduate student done it by himself) claiming that either Bar–Meir’s work was known or if the work was not known it must be wrong, here is a challenge for this minion and his masters and the other minions. Additionally there are those who quietly belief in these claims without advertise their belief, for example, Christopher Kent from DARPA. Kent used the typical talking about “you did not convince me because . . .” fill the blank for something that was not stated. However, Kent is afraid to convince or discuss this issue in any format because he know that he is wrong and he has to defend the establishment. Furthermore, there are those who like to put the horse blindfold to minimize their exposure the new technology like Carolyn Q. Judge so they will not realize their work was futile. With about five billion dollars a year in research grants from the united nation and additional billions from other sources the establishment will continue producing research papers which violate the second law of thermodynamics and Newton’s law.

It is time to examine these claims. This author is calling for disputation since the subject is science and true matter. If you believe in one or more of the topics below you have an invitation for disputation.

These topics are

1. The pivot point of the rolling or pitching is either in the metacenter or mass centroid or “rolling center” or “somewhere between the metacenter and gravity centroid”. The rolling center mentioned in this paper.
2. If you believe that there are really added mass matrix. In other words, if you believe that there are m_{ji} (or a_{ij}).
3. The moment of inertia is independent of the pivot point.
4. Added mass or the added moment of inertia is constant. As the governing equations as defined in Fossen or MIT or Caroline Judge’s classes.
5. The pivot point is constant in the ship navigation equations especially for unrsymmetrical.
6. If you believe that MMG equations are correct or logical or sensible.
7. If you believe the strip theory as is described or is correct as in MIT’s classes.
8. If you believe that added mass is not actually a single added mass (a core belief in the common establishment’s doctrine).
9. If you believe that more 20% of the world research in the ship stability/navigation does not violate the second law of thermodynamics or Newton’s second law.
10. \mathbf{GM} is the correct righting arm of the ship.

Acknowledgment

These papers set describes a progress in this kind of magnitude must have some willing and unwilling partners. First, thank you again for Naomi Marshak who corrected the English of early draft of the first 7 pages which her questions added more material. No one can clean all the English errors that this first author capable to produce, Second, thank you to the unwilling participants such as Christopher Kent from DARPA for protecting his job and readers from knowing the true, Carolyn Q. Judge from USNA that set to “protect” her students from the truth. Mathias Marley his lack of understating and willingness to curse this author brought the coupling issue was so inspiring (seriously). At least as opposed to the other minions who demand to remain anonymous, he was welling to show his name.

As example of fad’s believer Dr. Song from Department of Naval Architecture & Ocean Engineering, Inha University provided inspiration on how one can double down on stupidity is so amusing. There are those to contribute via discussions but asked to remain anonymous, thank you! Also thank you to Kostas Spyrou by his plagiarizing demonstrated how the establishment deals with the “rogue agent” by netscaping his/their material. You should be proud!

About the Author

As opposed to many other researchers, this author does not brag about how many citations his work has or jobs he held but only points to how many breakthroughs he has made and on how many people plagiarized his work. In the die casting industry, he has revolutionized the field by solving several major open questions. These questions include the critical plunger velocity, pQ^2 diagram, intensification pressure and critical vent area etc (for those who not familiar with die casting, these are the main pliers of die casting.). It has to be mentioned that the die casting establishment believed in solutions which violated the second law of the thermo and has spent millions promoting these beliefs (like the woke religion). Since the problems were not solved, literally hundreds of CFD teams from all over the world attempted to solve the problem in vain where this author solved them. The establishment fought against publishing these discoveries. The irony is that these author’s models today are undisputed and accepted in the industry.

Furthermore, this servant solved several open problems in shock dynamics and potential of compressed substances. Additionally, this author solved the deep ocean pressure and speed of sound which many oceanographers failed to calculate (Pushka Equation). Bar–Meir was instrumental in developments of the added mass (properties) concepts. He has differentiated between the added properties and the transfer properties. He discovered the change of the added mass and its effects on the governing equations. He invented the stability dome for floating bodies and in the process developed the equation for centroid

of circle segment.

Kostas J. Spyrou, when he gave his keynote lecture, basically copied many concepts that were developed by Bar-Meir (such as the stability dome) and presented them as his ideas. These concepts had never appeared in the literature before. It is interesting to point out that Dr. Spyrou has been observed downloading Bar-Meir's book. Dr. Spyrou's behavior is not unique to him only, Dr. Kenneth Brezinsky went out of his way to declare that Bar-Meir's calculations of compressible gas potential were useless and baseless. However, Brian J. Cantwell from Stanford University recently decided to copy Bar-Meir's idea and to dedicate a whole section (2.9) to it in his book (and probably also in his classes) to this idea. Except that Dr. Cantwell oversimplified the idea (he removed the dimensionless presentation), maybe because he did not fully understand it. The ship stability went major revision and basically revolutionize the field in particular the added mass (properties). The old governing equations yielding hundreds percent errors had to be modified due to discoveries of this author. In fact, Bar-Meir demonstrate almost all paper published in marine engineering are fatality futile.

Conflict of Interest

The authors certify that they have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity or person with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent–licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials or individuals discussed in this manuscript.

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